

**Aileen Fyfe, Professor
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Senior scholars to drive open access for books

– Aileen Fyfe

It is time for senior scholars to embrace open access publishing for books – demonstrating that it’s just as credible, just as scholarly, and will lead to more readers, a wider variety of readers and a stronger profile.

Aileen Fyfe, Professor of Modern History at the University of St Andrews, published her first open access book in 2022, in collaboration with three postdoc researchers. *A History of Scientific Journals*, it wasn’t initially conceived as an open access publication, but three things changed Fyfe’s mind.

The switch to open access

Soon after Fyfe started the AHRC-funded research in 2013, looking at the history of academic publishing from the 17th century to the present day (including open access), she signed with an established press. But, given the nature of the topic, it felt increasingly odd to not move with the times and publish openly.

The book was also long, far longer than traditional presses like – at one point, Fyfe was told it might have to be split into three volumes.

She explained:

“We didn’t want to do that, because it would be the sort of thing that’s priced at £300, sits on library shelves in perhaps 200 locations around the world... and nobody ever reads it! We wanted people to read our book.”

Nor could they trim the wordcount – the book is a chronological history spanning 350 years, so there was a lot of important information to explore to do the topic justice.

Switching mindset

The biggest hurdle, however, was the fear factor. As an established scholar, Fyfe was happy to go open access, but she was concerned it might damage the career prospects of the postdoc researchers she was working with. But, one of the postdoc researchers was a strong advocate for open access and persuaded her otherwise.

Fyfe said:

“Her confidence in it enabled me to feel that I wouldn’t be doing a bad thing by the postdoc researchers if we went ahead with open access.”

So Fyfe switched to an open access publisher who didn’t place any restrictions on the length of the book or the number of illustrations it contained.

Open access = more readers

Going open access has led to a much larger and diverse readership and greater visibility for Fyfe and her researchers. As soon as the book was published, it started clocking up views – 1,800 downloads in the first month. In comparison, Fyfe’s previous best-selling book totalled just 865 sales in more than 15 years.

Fyfe says the fact it is easily and freely available makes a huge difference, and in many ways. She explained:

“ I can give a talk, put the link up and know that people in the audience will be clicking on the link right away and having a look. And it’s so easy for the link to be shared online. This has made our book visible to many more people, including people who aren’t historians, but are interested in the contemporary challenges of academic publishing.

And one of the postdoc researchers has since published her second open access book.

Born digital

Fyfe also likes the fact that open access publishers think digitally – books are born digital. This breaks down traditional barriers around pagination, the number of illustrations, the form the output takes, etc.

She said:

“There’s a flexibility that lets you produce a product that fits the project you’re doing. You can experiment more.”

The role of senior academics

It was a postdoc who convinced Fyfe to switch to open access, but Fyfe thinks senior academics should be leading the charge. She said:

***“ Change has to come from more established scholars. We need to see senior members of the profession speaking out in favour, demonstrating that it can be done and that the publishing process is very similar in terms of editorial boards, peer review, copy editing etc. And that it’s not an inferior product, either intellectually or as a reading experience.*”**

Fyfe says there are several myths about open access that need debunking – such as that it will damage people’s careers because publishing open access is less prestigious than traditional publishing – and that senior members of the academic community need to get on board and demonstrate otherwise.